

Phytochemical Investigation of *Cassia glauca* Bark

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Cassia glauca is a well-known plant belonging to the family leguminosae and is reputed in Indian System of Medicine¹. The present communication reports the isolation and structure elucidation of two anthraquinones, chrysophanol and physcion from the stem bark of *C. glauca* collected from Allahabad. Identity of the plant was confirmed by the Botanical Survey of India, Allahabad. The structures of compounds were confirmed by colour reactions, spectral data and by comparison with authentic samples.

Air-dried and powdered stem bark (4 kg) was extracted with boiling ethanol and the concentrated extract poured into ice-cold water to give water-soluble and -insoluble fractions. The water-insoluble fraction was extracted successively with hexane, benzene and ethyl acetate in a soxhlet extractor. The ethyl acetate fraction on chromatography over silica gel column using petroleum ether-benzene (8 : 2) as eluant gave a yellow coloured compound-A (350 mg). Further elution with benzene-chloroform (6 : 4) afforded the shining orange coloured compound-B (250 mg). Compound-A and compound-B gave characteristic colour reaction of anthraquinone².

Compound-A, m.p. 195⁰, C₁₅H₁₀O₄ (M⁺ 254) : $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 150 (chelated phenolic OH), 1 660 (non-chelated C=O) and 1 625 cm⁻¹ (chelated C=O); ¹H nmr δ 2.45 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.09 (1H, brs, ArH, H-2), 7.3–7.65 (4H, m, ArH), 12.10 and 11.99 (two chelated hydroxyl), responded positively to the methanolic magnesium acetate test³ for an α -hydroxyanthraquinone and was characterised as chrysophanol¹ by direct comparison (m.m.p., co-tlc and co-ir) with an authentic sample.

Compound-B, m.p. 207⁰, C₁₆H₁₂O₅ (M⁺ 284) ; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 2 940 (phenolic OH), 1 660 (non-chelated C=O) and 1 635 cm⁻¹ (chelated C=O); ¹H nmr δ 2.42 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.91 (3H, s, OCH₃)⁵, 6.66 and 7.34 (each 1H, d, J 2 Hz, H-2 and H-4), 7.05 and 7.59 (each 1H, d, J 3 Hz, H-7 and H-5), 12.08 and 12.28 (each broad singlet exchangeable with D₂O, 1H, 2 × OH, C-8 and C-1), was characterised as physcion by direct comparison (m.m.p., co-tlc) with an authentic sample.

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